

GREEN LABS

A simple guide to
more sustainable
research

About the green lab guide

What is the purpose of this guide?

The aim of this guide is to provide a set of straightforward actions and changes that anyone interested in sustainable research can implement in their laboratory or research environment. While this guide doesn't cover every aspect of sustainable research, it serves as a starting point to inspire you and your team to take the first steps toward more environmentally friendly research practices.

Who is this guide for?

This guide is designed for anyone involved in research who wants to adopt more sustainable practices. Whether you're working in a lab, studying as a student, or managing research administration, there's something here for you. Each section includes a header that clearly indicates who it's intended for, making it easy to find relevant advice.

What if I don't find this guide helpful?

We have tried to make the Green Guide applicable to many researchers across many research fields. However, if you don't find this guide useful we suggest that you search online and through organisations such as LEAF for information on sustainable research.

Can I share this guide with others?

Yes, please do! This guide was made to be shared with as many people as possible.

Who made this guide?

This guide was made by CPR Goes Green, a grassroots initiative at the Center for Protein Research, University of Copenhagen.

General advice

Take one step at a time

Making a lab sustainable might seem overwhelming, but tackling challenges one step at a time can increase the chances of success and team engagement. Involving your team in the decision-making process helps significantly when implementing behavioural changes, ensuring everyone feels part of the journey.

Set clear goals

Focusing your efforts is much easier when you have a defined goal to guide you. Setting specific, measurable goals helps you track progress and clearly see the impact of your efforts.

Celebrate successes

Remember to celebrate your achievements, whether it's reaching a specific goal or implementing a new sustainable practice. Making your lab more sustainable should be an enjoyable and motivating experience, and celebrating small wins will help keep the momentum going.

Learn from others

Many others have already developed strategies, methods, and tools to help transition toward sustainability. There's no need to reinvent the wheel; take advantage of the resources, ideas, and knowledge that others have already created. Building on their experience can make your journey smoother and more efficient. So, ask around among colleagues and collaborators, or search for ongoing initiatives at other universities and institutions.

If you work in...

Dry labs and compute infrastructure

1

Clean up your data storage

Clearing out old storage is a good way to stay organized and reduce the overall clutter of your work. Moving and sending large datasets uses considerable amounts of energy, so try to keep as few copies of large datasets as possible and make sure your team is using the same versions. A 30-min data-clearing-hackathon in your team can do wonders for the organization and clutter of your data.

2

Measure your energy use

Different projects will require different amounts of computing power and hence energy. Mapping which projects use large amounts of compute will help your team prioritize just like you do with finances and time. Dedicated tools such as [Green Algorithms](#) and [codegreen](#) already exist.

3

Update or change your software

For many scientific analyses there are several available software tools. These may vary greatly in their resource requirements and energy use. Using a different software or a newer version of the same software can reduce the energy consumed by several orders of magnitude. [1]

Resources

Articles

“Ten simple rules to make your computing more environmentally sustainable” - [10.1371/journal.pcbi.1009324](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1009324)

“How to stop data centres from gobbling up the world’s electricity” - [10.1038/d41586-018-06610-y](https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-018-06610-y)

Apps for more sustainable code

Green Algorithms - <https://www.green-algorithms.org/>

codegreen - codegreen-client.readthedocs.io/en/

Green software Foundation - <https://greensoftware.foundation>

Country-related carbon intensities of energy

Check [OurWorldInData](#) or [the International Energy Agency](#) (IEA)

Knowledge

The location of your computer facilities matter. The CO₂ emitted for each kWh of energy consumed is around 17 times higher in Australia than in Iceland. [2]

Electricity consumption from a single computer scientist may be equivalent to that of **100** european citizens. [2]

50%-80% of an electronic device's carbon footprint stems from production. [3]

Training a large AI model can emit almost **five times** the lifetime emissions of an average American car. [4]

If you work in...

Wet labs and core laboratory facilities

1

Join a certification program

There is no need to reinvent the wheel. Certifications like [LEAF](#) or [My Green Lab](#) offer certifications that provide a structured framework and reference for wet lab-related practices, along with numerous resources to help you begin.

2

Turn off / tune down your equipment

Much equipment comes with options for running at different settings, some with much lower energy requirements. For example, ultra-low temperature freezers can easily be turned from -80°C to -70°C reducing the energy consumption by around one third.[5] Also, make sure to turn off your equipment when it is not in use.

3

Plan your experiments with purpose

Even small improvements to your experimental setup may reduce the need for repeat- and follow up experiments. Invest time in carefully setting experimental conditions and selecting only essential samples and materials. Analyse data immediately and record your findings thoroughly. These habits conserve resources and time, but they also help you stay organized and motivated for your next discovery!

Resources

Lab certifications

- [LFAF certification](#)
- [My green lab certification](#)

Resources / locations for more sustainable lab practices

- [freezer challenge](#)
- [Greenvourlab.org](#)
- [LFAF Resources and Materials](#)
- [Sels Network](#)

Articles

"Facing sustainability in the lab"

<https://www.rdworldonline.com/facing-sustainability-in-the-lab/>

"What can you do to make your lab greener"

<https://www.nature.com/articles/d41586-020-01368-8>

"Labs should cut plastic waste too"

<https://www.nature.com/articles/528479c>

"The relevance of sustainable laboratory practices"

<https://doi.org/10.1039/D4SU00056K>

Knowledge

Fume cupboards can use 3.5 x as much energy as an average US home. [6]

The annual amount of plastic waste produced by laboratories worldwide is **5.5 mio. tonnes**. That's nearly the weight of the Great Pyramid of Giza.[8]

60% of the water and electricity consumed at many universities is consumed in laboratory buildings. [7]

If you work as a ...

Leader or Principal Investigator

1

Organize a “Green initiative” meeting

Engaging your team in the sustainability journey is essential for success. Start off with a session where you and your team gather ideas, address concerns, and build excitement. Ideally, you can use this session to create a shared goal that everyone feels motivated to work toward.

2

Set a clear initial goal for your lab

Clear, measurable goals give your group something concrete to work towards. For example, “Look through all standard protocols to see if waste can be reduced” is simple, measurable, and worth celebrating if achieved. For inspiration, check out certification programs such as LEAF or My green lab.

3

Appoint a “green” coordinator

Progress is much more likely if everyone knows who is the main driver of green efforts. Whether it be you, a lab technician or an engaged post doc in your lab, having a “green” coordinator will make it clear whose job it is to keep track of your group’s progress and will also show that your group is making structural changes. Make sure that the coordinator has allocated time for their new responsibilities.

Resources

Articles

"We are all in this together: engaging employees on sustainability"

– <https://www.theguardian.com/sustainable-business/employees-engaged-sustainability-how>

"How to Get Your Team on Board with a Major Change"

– <https://hbr.org/2022/08/how-to-get-your-team-on-board-with-a-major-change>

Arguments for added sustainability measures

Finances:

Sustainable practices can offer significant savings by reducing the quantity of materials and energy used.

Funding:

More funding agencies are prioritizing sustainability in their assessments (e.g. MSCA postdoctoral fellowship).

Recruitment:

Sustainability can attract more young scientists; having measures in place can help recruit new talents.

Image & outreach:

By promoting green initiatives and being a frontrunner, you signal to others that your institute is pushing boundaries and is worth following and collaborating with.

Community:

Setting and reaching green goals in your team is a good way to foster community and boost morale. This can be much needed relief, especially in periods when scientific progress is slow. Starting green initiatives also give reasons to connect with other teams around the world, whom you can engage with to share lessons and experiences.

If you work in...

Management and Administration

1

Put sustainability on the agenda

Change won't happen by itself. Work towards getting sustainability on the agenda at recurring meetings, so that it is has a clear priority along other topics such as safety, economy, etc. This also sends a strong signal to other members of your institution that sustainability is being prioritized.

2

Check available sustainable options

Sustainable choices should ideally be the easy/comfortable option, especially when expecting behavioural change. Check availability of sustainable options such as ordering/billing train tickets, purchasing lab equipment from sustainable suppliers, and sharing and repairing of equipment and resources across departments.

3

Engage with green initiatives

Chances are, there is already a group of individuals in your department/institute that are working to make their research more sustainable. Engage with them through regular meetings to celebrate their progress and help support their actions. Making such meetings open may also encourage more people to join thus fostering engagement and impact.

Knowledge

\$250,000

were saved annually at the University of Colorado Boulder Cell Culture Facility by sharing lab facilities between groups. [9]

84%

of respondents to a survey from the Royal Society of Chemistry agreed that they would like to do more to reduce the impact of their scientific work on the environment. [7]

References used in this guide

1. Grealey, Jason, Loïc Lannelongue. "The Carbon Footprint of Bioinformatics." *Molecular Biology and Evolution* 2022;39:3. doi:10.1093/molbev/msac034.
2. International Energy Agency, Energy statistics data browser, <https://www.iea.org/data-and-statistics/data-tools/energy-statistics-data-browser>
3. Singh N, Ogunseitan OA. Disentangling the worldwide web of e-waste and climate change co-benefits. *Circular Economy*. 2022;1(2):100011. doi:10.1016/j.cec.2022.100011.
4. Hao, K., 'Training a single AI model can emit as much carbon as five cars in their lifetimes', MIT Technology Review, 2019, <https://www.technologyreview.com/2019/06/06/239031/training-a-single-ai-model-can-emit-as-much-carbon-as-five-cars-in-their-lifetimes>
5. Gumapas LAM, Simons G. Factors affecting the performance, energy consumption, and carbon footprint for ultra low temperature freezers: case study at the National Institutes of Health. *World Rev Sci Technol Sustain Dev*. 2013;10(1-3):129-41.
6. Mills E, Sartor D. Energy use and savings potential for laboratory fume hoods. *Energy*. 2005;30:1859-64. doi:10.1016/j.energy.2004.11.003.
7. Royal Society of Chemistry Sustainable Laboratories: A Community-wide Movement toward Sustainable Laboratory Practices, Cambridge, 2022
8. Urbina M, Watts A, Reardon E. Labs should cut plastic waste too. *Nature*. 2015;528:479. doi:10.1038/528479c.
9. C. Greever , T. Nahreini and K. Rimrez-Aguilar , A Case Study of the Biochemistry Cell Culture Facility at the , University of Colorado, Boulder, Colorado, 2018

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